

THE PURPOSE OF MEANINGFUL ENGAGEMENT: A WORKBOOK FOR THOSE WORKING WITH PEOPLE LIVING WITH DEMENTIA IN RESIDENTIAL CARE SETTINGS

A reflective tool for all staff to understand the purpose of meaningful activities and occupation and recognise what successful engagement means.

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The meaning of occupation is subject to the world view of the person with dementia, caregivers and available occupational opportunities...

A supportive environment can ensure occupations and activities are meaningful

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1 Introduction

How somebody spends their time has a huge impact on how they feel. This includes how they see themselves and how satisfied they feel that they are living life in the way they want to. Feeling happy with life may not mean feeling occupied every moment, but that the things people do have a personal meaning to them. This is just as true for somebody living with dementia as for those without it.

When we think of activities for people living with dementia, all too often we imagine tasks or games. These may well hold a great deal of value but other less organised things, such as sitting in silent companionship, might also have just as great a value for someone. Instead of focusing on what different types of activities can be used to support someone living with dementia, this workbook aims to get us to think about what the purpose of our engagement is. It will look at how the way someone is occupied makes them feel and what affect we, as carers, hope that different activities and occupations will have.

If we, and the people we are hoping to support, are trying to achieve different things this can lead to conflict and frustration. It is important to reflect on *why* we are doing the things we do and how we feel in order to find a path that we can tread together.

Glossary of terms:

- **Meaningful Occupation:**
How the person living with dementia occupies their time; this could be an obvious activity or task or something less obvious such as enjoying a moment of peace. The person is engaged in a way which gives meaning.
- **Functional skills and activities:**
Activities which support the person to meet the demands of daily life such as getting dressed independently.

2 How to use this workbook

This workbook is designed as a reflection tool for all staff working in residential care homes. The activities in the workbook help you to think about what you, and those around you, value. The questions can be answered individually, or you may prefer to discuss them with others.

Each part begins with a description of the theory about why activities and engagement might be meaningful for someone living with dementia and then is followed by an interactive section for you to reflect on your own experiences. These do not need to be completed in order. The supporting ideas cards are each labelled to match the relevant section in the workbook and can help you think of ways that you could put the theory into practice.

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3 How we think

The reason somebody chooses to do something can be very different for different people. Even something like the time of day might change why we choose to engage with an activity. An example could be reading. You may read before going to sleep to help relax after a busy day, or during the day you may need important information for work which you have to read. Both activities can be described as reading but have very different purposes.

Providing opportunities to feel meaningfully engaged is very important as part of caring for people with dementia. However, it can be hard to know how to support somebody to be occupied in a meaningful way if we don't know what we are hoping to achieve through our engagement or activities. Are they to fill the time? Or to help somebody keep the skills that help them feel more independent? Or perhaps to help manage anxiety and frustration? Without knowing what we aim to get from these activities it is difficult to know how successful they are and if we need to do anything differently.

What we believe are the most important reasons for doing an activity will often influence what activities we are most likely to support and how we judge if they have been successful. To judge if engagement is having a positive impact, we need to consider what the person with dementia wants from it, what we hope it will do, and if these things are the same.

By knowing how we think about what the purpose of activities should be, we can spot our strengths and also consider if there are things we do not do, but could do. Through this reflection we can examine if we could create different chances for people to feel occupied that we had not previously considered.

The four characters in this workbook are based on different ways that research has found people working in dementia care settings think about what the purpose of activities should be. Throughout this workbook we will look at different things somebody with dementia might gain from being meaningfully occupied. We will also look at how each of the characters might view the different outcomes of the activities. Read each one and note down anything you agree or disagree with, and how *you* feel about the possible different purposes of activities for people living with dementia.

You may feel you agree more with a one character's way of thinking, or that you agree and disagree with different aspects of each character. You may relate to different characters for each different section. The characters are there to help you think about how you think!

There is no correct way of thinking, all of the characters have different strengths and weaknesses in different situations.

Care worker A

A believes that activities can give people living with dementia an opportunity to feel like their lives have purpose and they are still valued. It is important to A that they are helping people with dementia to still be able to make decisions about their lives and how they spend their time. A is very good at adapting activities so that the people they support are able to continue to do things by themselves and have a feeling of accomplishment.

Care worker B

B believes that the way a person with dementia occupies themselves should help to bring them comfort and happiness. B sees activities as a way to help bring calmness to the person living with dementia and help to distract them from negative emotions and loneliness. They see this as creating a calm and safe environment. B is very good at demonstrating to the people they care for that they are interested in them and want to spend time in their company

Care worker C

C sees activities as a chance to show kindness and love to people with dementia. C sees it as their responsibility to help the person remember the things that mattered to them through activities such as reminiscence. C is good at creating activities which immerse the person with dementia in sensation without them having to think about what to do or worrying about doing something wrong. They believe activities can be a good way for families to see their loved one with dementia is still the same person.

Care Worker D

D values activities as a way of holding off the effects of dementia and helping the person with dementia to retain their skills for as long as possible. D values activities which promote physical ability such as exercise but also that reduce the need for medication. D is good at creating opportunities for the person with dementia to see the things they can still do.

4 The different reasons for activities

There are many ways that being occupied and being involved in activities can be meaningful for someone with dementia. The diagram below shows the different reasons that research has suggested activities can be meaningful. The two main purposes are represented by the green tree, describing how being occupied can help someone feel that their life has meaning, and by the blue shed, describing how occupation can be used as a tool. These are influenced by the environment, shown by the mustard-coloured root circles. Everything is influenced by how the person living with dementia, and those working with them, view the world, this is represented by the people with binoculars.

This workbook will break down the diagram below into smaller sections, looking at each part more closely and asking you to think about your feelings in relation to its elements.

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Activities and feeling meaningfully in engaged in life help the person living with dementia to feel fulfilled. Lots of different elements are important to achieve this. Some things will be more important to one person than another, and the things which seem most important may change many times. However, it is important to remember that we can't assume we know what is important to someone. We must create opportunities for people to have different experiences to know how someone feels. A larger version of this diagram can be seen on the inside cover and back page of this workbook.

4.1 Living a meaningful life

The tree looks at the different things which help a person with dementia to feel they are living a meaningful life.

4.1.1 Link to past identity, and opportunities for an evolving and changing identity.

For many people with dementia, feeling “normal” becomes very important. This doesn’t necessarily mean doing the things that somebody did before their dementia; it means doing things which make them feel like themselves, often everyday things they would previously think of as mundane. This is important to

help people living with dementia to see themselves as more than an “ill person”. Doing things which make people feel normal can be very important during a time of uncertainty and changes. Dementia can make people feel that they no longer fit into their life and moving into a residential care setting can make this feeling stronger. Activities which make somebody feel they still have a place and are still fundamentally the same person can be very important at a time when the things they have taken for granted about themselves are threatened.

Trying new things can help people to feel normal too. Often the things people did in the past can become more challenging and highlight the skills that the person has lost. Trying new things gives the person living with dementia a chance to see themselves in a new light. Gaining new interests can make change they see in themselves through dementia seem less upsetting as their interests evolve rather than just drop off.

Care worker A

A feels it is important for people with dementia to feel satisfied with their lives and so they strongly believe in the importance of activities as a way of building self-worth and exploring new ways for people to see themselves. A believes that throughout their experience of dementia, people have preferences and that they can still have meaningful experience even though they are different from previous interests.

Care worker B

B sees it as important to avoid the person living with dementia feeling that they can no longer do something as this could cause distress and frustration. They value the activities which support reminiscence and those which bring joy and happiness to the person with dementia but without highlighting lost skills. For B it is more important for the person to feel happy in the moment than to think about how they may have changed.

Care worker C

C values activities which help to hold on to the identity of the person before they started living with dementia. They see it as important to show the person and their loved ones that they have not changed. Reminiscence is very important to C as they see themselves as an anchor to help the person with dementia hold on to the things which were important to them throughout the advancement of their dementia. Exploring how someone's preferences change and finding new activities are less important to C.

Care Worker D

D values activities with a more therapeutic outcome rather than those which are about exploring identity. Activities which support memory and communication such as reminiscence are highly valued but more for their ability to slow the progression of the person's dementia. D believes that both new activities and the activities someone previously did can be valuable though as a means to remain active and alert.

What do you think?

Do you agree with any views of the characters above?

Is there anything you disagree with?

What do you think about the idea of activities helping someone with dementia to feel normal, to feel unchanged, or to feel they are evolving?

Do you think that someone can accept dementia as a new part of themselves and still feel satisfied with their life?

4.1.2 Full Spectrum of Experience

For most people, life has highs and lows and many different experiences. People will seek variety in their experience of emotions too. This could be through watching a scary movie or listening to a sad song. For many people, difficult experiences and negative emotions can be an important part of their life. An example is bereavement due to the loss of a spouse or child. The loss hurts; however, to not mention it or think about it would stop the person from fully feeling themselves. Likewise, many people living with dementia value feelings of intimacy or sexual desire. Moving to residential care settings can threaten these relationships. The beliefs and values of the people around them will have a huge impact on how someone is able to experience feelings of intimacy.

Variety in a person's environment also helps to create a feeling of being complete. This might mean someone feeling the sun on their face, feeling waves lapping over their feet or smelling flowers. Always staying in the same place, despite it being comfortable, can lead to people feeling diminished. Having access to a variety of environments can prompt a variety of feelings and a sense of fulfilment.

Another important part of the full spectrum of experience is to feel absorbed in something without the need for thought. These ways of being occupied are free from failure, success or judgement, but are just about experiencing life in that exact moment.

Care worker A

A considers emotional fulfilment as a very important part of their activities. They see a variety of experiences as a key part of this. A particularly promotes activities that help the person with dementia to feel a sense of achievement. A agrees being immersed in an activity is very positive, though they also greatly value being able to reflect on a sense of achievement from feeling successful. A feels it is important that people with dementia can have the opportunity for intimate relationships.

Care worker B

B tries to avoid topics or activities which they think will cause distress or upset. They feel that, while the person with dementia experiences the emotion, they will soon forget the reason why, leaving the person confused and vulnerable. B generally thinks that the comfort of familiar routines and surroundings can help the person with dementia to feel safe. Though B sees that using 'muscle memory' and automatic skills for activities can make it easier for people, they feel that one of the most important reasons for activities is to build relationships and it is important that this isn't lost.

Care worker C

C feels it is important to support people with dementia to remember the things they cared about and the people they love, but that it is just important to avoid things which are likely to make someone sad. C values activities that require little thought. They see these as keeping the person with dementia busy and avoiding boredom. C is concerned that sexual or intimate relationships could lead to harm, due to difficulty for people with dementia to consent and concern that families will be distressed by new intimate relationships.

Care Worker D

D feels automatic skills should be supported as these will help to keep the skills needed for independence. Feeling absorbed in an activity without a need for thought is not seen as important as maintaining functional skills. Though D wants the people living with dementia which they care for to feel happy, they see activities as primarily a means to slow the progression of the dementia.

What do you think?

Do you agree with any views of the characters above?

Is there anything you disagree with?

How do you think emotions such as grief and sadness affect people living with dementia in the shorter and longer term?

Do you believe that it is important to support new or existing sexual and intimate relationships for people living with dementia?

4.1.3 Making a contribution

Research has found that it can be important for people living with dementia to feel they are contributing in some way. This could mean making decisions about how they live their life (such as what they eat or if they smoke), how they influence the people around them (such as giving advice or helping to interview new staff), or even the impact they have on the wider world (such as creating a memoir for future generations or being involved in expert by experience groups).

For people living in residential care settings, making decisions about how they live their lives is influenced by their environment. Being involved in decision making is only beneficial if the person feels that their views are valued and the reason for the choice is genuine. People living in residential care settings can feel that they have little influence in their home: having choice about their environment can help this. Choices may be simple, such as whether to open a window or how to arrange furniture, or maybe bigger choices, such planning new décor or selecting a pet. However, living with other people can lead to tension from multiple people trying to influence the environment to match their own tastes.

Having other people accept and recognise that the person with dementia can contribute something helps to motivate them to want to be actively involved. Contributions can be practical but equally they might mean contributing to a conversation or relationship. Showing affection, such as writing a card for a carer, helps to make the relationship feel more reciprocal.

For some people living with dementia, it is still important to contribute to life outside of a residential care setting. This might mean keeping a role in their family or the local community. Volunteering roles, expert by experience groups, blogging or voting in elections can help someone to still feel a part of a wider community.

What about independence?

Independence is something that many people strive for and value highly, however, with the progression of dementia independence will be ever more limited. The language we use and the person's experience can change the way people view independence. If doing things together is felt as a positive experience by the person with dementia it helps to reduce the feelings of frustration and loss they may experience as they rely more on others. If we emphasise the value of working together as a community through things such as gardening, cooking, or caring for each other, it ensures the people we care for have a chance to see themselves as an important part of the group rather than just dependant on it.

Care worker A

A believes it is really important for people living with dementia to have personal choice over their life. They see being able to influence the environment as a big part of this. Though A is aware that having more than one person make decisions about shared spaces could cause tension, they feel the overall benefits to individuals are worth the risk. A focuses more on the individual preferences of the person living with dementia than their role as part of a community.

Care worker B

B will try to avoid distress or conflict between the people living in their care. B believes individual choice is important, however, if somebody's actions are causing others to feel distressed B will try to diffuse the situation through techniques such as distraction. B feels uncomfortable with the idea of the person with dementia doing wider community activities, such as being an expert by experience or voting, as they are concerned that the potential pressure of such decisions would leave the person living with dementia feeling anguished.

Care worker C

C believes that their role in helping a person living with dementia to feel loved is a key purpose of activities. They strongly value small group activities and working together as a way to bring people closer and show affection. C is less focused on supporting people living with dementia to make decisions or to feel they are able to change their surroundings. Independence is seen by C as adding unnecessary stress when they should be supporting the person to feel happy and calm.

Care Worker D

D considers keeping independence for as long as possible the most important purpose of activities. They value anything which helps to maintain the skills of the person living with dementia. D sees making a contribution is useful if it helps to preserve physical health and memory. They are less focused on how making a contribution might make the person with dementia feel in the short term. They believe that holding off the progression of dementia and staying as independent as possible in the long term is the best way to help someone feel more satisfied with their life.

What do you think?

Do you agree with any views of the characters above?

Is there anything you disagree with?

How do you think a residential care setting could ensure that people living with dementia were genuinely involved in the day-to-day organisation?

Do you think it is a good idea to try and influence how somebody living with dementia thinks about their independence? How do you imagine they might feel?

4.2 Occupation and activities as a tool

This part of the diagram looks at how being occupied and doing activities can be used as a tool to create a specific outcome.

4.2.1 Occupation as a tool to manage emotion and behaviour

Activities can be used as a tool to achieve a particular outcome, such as relieving frustration or keeping fit, both by people living with dementia and by those who support them. Being occupied can be a good way to help to cope with difficult emotions in the short term. People with dementia have described how they can use activities to distract themselves from anxiety or feeling low, to create moments of fun and joy, relieve boredom and to help them to feel relaxed. Occupation could also be used as a means to reduce medication use.

Managing behaviour using activities and staying occupied has been described by some care staff as helping improve quality of life and leading to feelings of fulfilment for people living with dementia. However, managing behaviour through activities was not mentioned in research by people living with dementia themselves. Some care staff use activities to distract people from things which may cause them harm, or to create a more harmonious environment in communal living settings. Using occupation to manage behaviour could cause tension if the person living with dementia feels their concerns and choices are being overlooked through being diverted.

Care worker A

A strongly feels that activities should not be about trying to influence someone's behaviour. To A, it is important that the person living with dementia can express themselves and choose how they spend their time. They consider the idea of trying to change somebody's actions or emotions to be dishonest or not respecting the experience of that person. A does agree it is important that people living with dementia have ways to help them to deal with their emotions if they choose to.

Care worker B

B sees creating a happy and calm environment as really important to help support the quality of life for people living with dementia. Helping someone to feel occupied is seen as the best way to support people to live together harmoniously and also to protect the person living with dementia from potential harm. B values activities as a way to relieve boredom and loneliness, and to avoid distressing feelings.

Care worker C

C believes that activities are beneficial to help avoid distress and frustration for people living with dementia, though using activities to help change behaviour was not considered as important. C sees activities as a way to help them demonstrate affection for the person with dementia. They consider these feelings of warmth and kindness as helping to manage negative emotions the person with dementia might be experiencing.

Care Worker D

D sees occupation as a key part of helping to reduce medication. They value activities that can redirect people living with dementia from behaviours which are challenging such a physical harm to themselves or others. They believe using activities in this way has the potential to reduce medication, such as antidepressants and sedatives, with the aim of improving the overall experience of the person with dementia.

What do you think?

Do you agree with any views of the characters above?

Is there anything you disagree with?

How do you feel about using occupation as a means to distract someone from particular emotions or behaviour?

Do you think it is possible to use occupation and activities as a way to reduce medication?

4.2.2 Occupation as a tool for therapeutic effect

Ensuring people are occupied can be used to keep both the body and the mind healthy. This could mean maintaining the existing skills of the person living with dementia, maintaining physical fitness and mobility, or slowing down the effects of dementia. Preserving skills can be seen as supporting independence and maintaining a sense of normality by both people living with dementia and those supporting them.

Some people living with dementia, and others who supported them, have reported that it is the responsibility of the person living with dementia to do all they can to maintain the best possible health and “fight” the dementia. Using occupation in this way can centre on the belief that it is important for people living with dementia to keep their life as close as possible to the life that they had before diagnosis. This could reduce their willingness to accept changes due to dementia and find new ways to feel fulfilled and satisfied with their life.

Care worker A

A views maintaining a level of independence as helpful in supporting someone to make choices and feel more in control of their lives. Physical health, such as good mobility, is valued as it enables people to access the things they value without having to rely as much on others. A views activities as an effective way to help someone to maintain the skills that are important to them or support functioning.

Care worker B

B does not consider the possible therapeutic effects of activities as being an important reason for undertaking them. B feels that as dementia is a progressive disease, "fighting" it will cause unnecessary stress. They believe the person with dementia will keep being negatively reminded that their skills are deteriorating. B sees activities as bringing joy and pleasure which help the person with dementia to enjoy their life without stress and pressure.

Care worker C

C does not see occupation as a means to slow the progression of someone's dementia, neither do they believe it is the responsibility of the person with dementia to try and keep their mind and body active. C believes it is part of their role to remind people living with dementia of the things which have mattered to them in the past. C considers it part of their job to hold on to the identity of the person living with dementia and therefore reduce the need for them to "fight" the effects of dementia.

Care Worker D

D strongly agrees that the most important purpose of activities should be to hold off the progression of dementia. They believe that the way a person is occupied should help to promote physical health and practical skills in order to maintain independence for as long as possible. D feels that engaging in activities has the potential to reduce the need for some medication. They see this as reducing possible side effects and subsequently the quality of the person's life.

Occupation
as a long term
therapeutic tool

What do you think?

Do you agree with any views of the characters above?

Is there anything you disagree with?

Do you think that trying to slow the progression of dementia can be achieved through activities? What occupations do you think might help with this?

How could you help someone with dementia to still feel they have control in their life if they have very limited mobility and rely on other people to move around?

4.2.3 Occupation as a method of assessment.

Both people living with dementia and the people who support them have described how they use different activities to see how much dementia symptoms have progressed. These could range from getting dressed, to things like remembering the names of family members. People living with dementia have described how they use activities to show others what they are capable of and to maintain their independence. The other side of this is that activities are often used as an indication of when a person living with dementia needs more support.

All four care worker characters use activities to gauge how someone with dementia is managing. This is usually through noticing if something has changed. It is important to remember that although dementia is progressive, for most people it is not a straight road. Many things can influence how someone living with dementia manages an activity. The difficulties they encounter may not be the same when they do the activity again. Frequently, a person may find they can do something some days but not all days. Not managing a task once does not mean that the skill is now lost permanently. Using activities as a gauge of progression needs to be done over multiple tries, looking for a change rather than basing any thoughts or actions on a single moment.

What do you think?

What potential risks might you imagine could stem from using activities to assess how someone's dementia has progressed?

How could you support a person with dementia if they were distressed because they were not able to do something which was very important to them?

4.3 Supportive Environment: How the surroundings affect the meaning of activities

The environment can change the meaning of why a person with dementia chooses to engage or not engage in an activity and why they feel this way. The four care worker characters are each influenced by the environment they work in and the demands of their job role. Though the four characters feel strongly about what activities should be for, other pressures can affect how they are able to support these activities.

The section below looks at how other people that the person with dementia lives with and the environment that they live in will influence how that person will want to be occupied and help to build motivation to engage in activities.

A supportive environment can ensure occupations and activities are meaningful

4.3.1 Bridging objects and subjects

Sometimes a trigger is needed to help start an activity or to help someone keep doing it. These triggers can be an object, a person or even a time of day. An example could be a duster - looking at it prompts an action. The trigger can help the person with dementia through reminding them what they were doing (in this case cleaning) or giving them time to gather their thoughts to carry on. It creates a bridge between the person and the activity which supports its continuation. These bridges can also help support conversations and connections between people.

4.3.2 Other's awareness of the person's intentions and choices

It can sometimes be very difficult for people in a supporting role to know how a person living with dementia really feels and what they want to do. This can be particularly difficult if the person with dementia has communication difficulties, or their words and their actions don't appear to match. It can also be hard for many people living in residential care settings to feel motivated to start something if they feel unsure of what they are "allowed" to do. Having different prompts and bridging objects can make it easier for us to recognise when somebody might want to be involved in an activity with a little encouragement. Having things going on in the environment might also help those who are not ready to do an activity, but who feel involved through watching others.

4.3.3 Other's seeing legitimacy in occupations

For people with dementia, feeling that how they choose to spend their time has a value can help to strengthen self-worth and identity. Often, the way other people react to an occupation influences how the person with dementia values it. If others dismiss an activity as trivial or not as important as their own task, this can reduce the likelihood of the desire of the person with dementia to maintain an activity or motivation to start something in the future. It is important to look for why something has value for the person living with dementia even if

it doesn't appear obvious. An example might be moving pieces of a jigsaw around without making the picture. It may seem outwardly an "incorrect" way to complete a puzzle, however it may be that grouping colours or patterns or shape offer relaxation and artistic worth to the person doing this.

4.3.4 The expectation a person with dementia can contribute.

For people living with dementia, it can be detrimental to see themselves as declining or no longer able to do something. People who support them often try to avoid situations in which someone may see themselves as failing. This can lead to limited opportunities for the person with dementia to try things and build a positive self-image. Assuming that everyone living with dementia has the potential to contribute in some way leads us to think in terms of how we can adjust the situation to make it accessible for them and what we mean by "contributing".

Somebody with advanced dementia may be able to indicate a preference for something like music or who they prefer to spend time with. This is a type of contribution that impacts on the person and those around them. These feelings of controlling the environment that the person lives in show that the person's choices matter and that they are valued.

What do you think?

Have you ever used an object, time of day or sound to help to build a connection with someone living with dementia? How do you think it helped you to communicate?

How might you support someone with dementia to choose if they want to be involved in an activity if they appear to be interested but also say no when asked?

How would you feel if a member of staff asked you to delay supporting a physical task such as monitoring health statistics because they and the person living with dementia were scrunching newspaper and it was making the person laugh?

Do you think that it is important for a person living with advanced dementia to influence their environment and why?

5 What does it mean for us?

All viewpoints bring something new and can bring a fresh way of looking at how to support people living with dementia.

The viewpoint of the person with dementia is very important in understanding what the purpose of occupation should be. They may well have different feelings and values to you, and if you value different things it becomes more challenging to say if the occupations available are meeting the needs of the person with dementia.

By ensuring the team share and celebrate the different ways of thinking about activities it becomes easier to recognise other people's perspectives and where their strengths might be. A team made up of different perspectives can be more responsive and flexible, adapting to the feelings of those they care for.

Everyone adds to a team, what do you bring to them?

In which ways do you think you are good at supporting someone living with dementia to feel involved in meaningful occupation?

When you are busy or stressed do you think that there are any of your beliefs or values which may get side-lined?

Looking back over the three sections do you think there are any things you could change in how you work?

As a group what are your strengths?

Do you think there are any areas of meaningful occupation that as a team you could develop?

Do you think there are any areas that you disagree with one another?

Your notes

6 Important considerations and useful resources

6.1 Consent:

It is important that consent is gained from the person involved in an activity. Consent doesn't have to be given verbally, but the person seeking consent must be confident that the person understands what is being asked of them and they can retain the information to be able to weigh up the pros and cons of taking part. On-going consent must also be considered, everyone has the right to change their mind. If a person indicates they wish to stop, this is then the removal of that consent. Valid consent can be hard to gauge as it can be difficult to assess the extent of understanding for some people or how much detail they have retained. It is important that the principles of the Mental Capacity Act are embedded in how you have these conversations, and where appropriate capacity assessments and subsequent Best Interest discussions are carried out and documented. Remember to start from a position of assuming the person has capacity to consent, but if you determine the person lacks capacity to consent then a Best Interest decision to consent can be made. For up to date information and guidance on complying with the Mental Capacity Act in the UK please visit <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/mental-capacity-act-making-decisions>.

6.2 Data protection:

It is essential to ensure there is a specific and legitimate reason for gathering and keeping data relating to people. This can include photography, videos or written documentation and related to both residents and others. Data must be kept securely in line with up-to-date policy and be destroyed when it is no longer needed. People can request to access their data. All data should be accurate, in-date, and personal opinions should be identified as such.

The meaning of occupation is subject to the world view of the person with dementia, caregivers and available occupational opportunities...